

APPENDIX P: Landscape Perception and Preference Survey Form (Digital Format)

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Envisioning Avenida, Recto, and Carriedo, Manila as Virtual Memoriscapes Through Immersive Mobile Technologies and Digital Heritage Interpretation

Landscape Perception and Preference Survey for the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip

Good day!

I am **Leijh Hanne Y. Alianza**, a senior undergraduate student from the University of the Philippines Diliman - College of Architecture under the Landscape Architecture program. I am currently conducting a study entitled **"Memoriscapes in Recto-spection: Envisioning Avenida, Recto, and Carriedo, Manila as Virtual Memoriscapes Through Immersive Mobile Technologies and Digital Heritage Interpretation"**. This study aims to create a Virtual Memoriscapes toolkit that seeks to reimagine the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip as a Virtual Memoriscapes through the co-design workshop sessions with the community and stakeholders of the study site as a demonstration of the toolkit. The study also aims to highlight the needs of the community and to showcase the significance of the study site as a former commercial and entertainment district through mobile augmented reality.

Part of my study consists of conducting a Landscape Perception and Preference Survey to determine the public's current perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, and their preferences on its surrounding open spaces and streetscapes. The results of this survey would be used as the basis for further investigations conducted in this study.

A portion of my methodology was based on Sundberg (2016), Hedblom et al (2019), Nadal, (2021), and Trias, (2022). These studies were used as reference for the present survey.

With this, I respectfully request your help in answering this short survey. In answering this survey, I will ensure that your answers are used only for this study, and that your personal data will be kept confidential and secure.

If you have any further questions, you may contact me via email at lyalianza@up.edu.ph.

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Magandang araw!

*Ako si **Leijh Hanne Y. Alianza**, isang mag-aaral sa ika-apat na taon sa Unibersidad ng Pilipinas Diliman - Kolehiyo ng Arkitektura sa ilalim ng programang Arkitekturang Hubog-Lupa. Ako ay kasalukuyang gumagawa ng aking tesis na pinamagatang, **"Memoriscapes in Recto-spection: Envisioning Avenida, Recto, and Carriedo, Manila as Virtual Memoriscapes Through Immersive Mobile Technologies and Digital Heritage Interpretation"**. Ang pag-aaral na ito ay naglalayong lumikha ng isang Virtual Memoriscapes toolkit na wariin ang Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip bilang isang Virtual Memoriscapes sa pamamagitan ng mga co-design workshop session kasama ang komunidad sa loob ng aking study site. Nilalayan din ng pag-aaral na ito na suriin ang mga pangangailangan ng komunidad, at ipakita ang kahalagahan ng lugar na ito bilang dating commercial at entertainment district sa pamamagitan ng mobile augmented reality.*

Ang isang bahagi ng aking pag-aaral ay ang pagsasagawa ng Landscape Perception at Preference Survey upang maimbestigahan ang pag-unawa ng publiko sa Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip sa kasalukuyan, at ang kanilang kagustuhan sa pagsasa-ayos ng mga luntiang pook at mga kalsada sa lugar na ito. Ang mga resulta ng sarbey na ito ay gagamitin batayan sa mga susunod na pagsisiyasat na gagawin sa pag-aaral na ito.

Bahagi ng aking metodolohiya ay pinagbasehan sa mga pag-aaral nina Sundberg (2016), Hedblom et al (2019), Nadal, (2021), at ni Trias, (2022). Ang mga pag-aaral na ito ay ginamit bilang sanggunian sa kasalukuyang sarbey.

Dahil rito, inaanyayahan ko kayo na sagutin ang maikling sarbey na ito. Sa pag-sagot ng sarbey na ito ay masisigurado kayo na ang inyong mga sagot ay gagamitin lang mismo para sa pag-aaral na ito, at ang inyong personal na datos ay mananatiling kumpidensyal at protektado.

Para sa mga karagdagang tanong, mangyaring mag-padala ng email sa lyalianza@up.edu.ph.

[Mag-sign in sa Google](#) para i-save ang iyong pag-usad. [Matuto pa](#)

* Tumutukoy sa kinakailangang tanong

DATA PRIVACY AND INFORMED CONSENT *

The data obtained from this survey will be treated as highly confidential and will be used exclusively for academic purposes. It will be kept anonymous in compliance with Republic Act (R.A) No. 10173, also known as the "Data Privacy Act of 2012". By consenting to participate in this survey, the student researcher is authorized to access and process your personal information. For more

Memoriscapes in Recto-spection: Visualizing Avenida, Recto, and Carriedo, Manila as Virtual Memoriscapes through immersive mobile technologies and digital heritage interpretation

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If you willingly and voluntarily agree to participate in this survey and have your personal data and information gathered and analyzed, please respond with YES. By answering YES in this consent form, you are allowing the researcher to use your responses for the thesis entitled "**Memoriscapes in Recto-spection: Envisioning Avenida, Recto, and Carriedo, Manila as Virtual Memoriscapes Through Immersive Mobile Technologies and Digital Heritage Interpretation**".

Ang datos na nakalap mula sa sarbey na ito ay ituturing na lubos na kumpidensyal at eksklusibong gagamitin para sa mga layuning pang-akademiko. Pananatilihin itong anonymous bilang pagsunod sa Republic Act (R.A.) No. 10173, na kilala rin bilang "Data Privacy Act of 2012". Sa pamamagitan ng pagpapayag na lumahok sa sarbey na ito, ang mag-aaral na mananaliksik ay awtorisado na i-access at iproseso ang iyong personal na impormasyon. Para sa karagdagang impormasyon sa Data Privacy Act of 2012, pahibisita ang sumusunod na link: <https://www.privacy.gov.ph/data-privacy-act/>.

Kung ikaw ay kusa at boluntaryong sumang-ayon na lumahok sa survey na ito at ang iyong personal na data at impormasyon ay makakalap at masuri, mangyaring tumugon ng OO. Sa pamamagitan ng pagsagot ng OO, pinapayagan mo ang mananaliksik na gamitin ang iyong mga tugon para sa tesis na pinamagatang "Memoriscapes in Recto-spection: Envisioning Avenida, Recto, and Carriedo, Manila as Virtual Memoriscapes Through Immersive Mobile Technologies and Digital Heritage Interpretation".

YES. I understand the aforementioned statement and hereby grant my consent to be part of this online survey as a qualified participant in accordance with the criteria of this study.

NO. I do not wish to take part in this study.

Susunod

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I-clear ang form

ABOUT THE SURVEY

This survey questionnaire consists of four parts which includes the following sections:

1. **Demographic Assessment** - Includes basic questions to record your demographic profile.
2. **Open-ended Questions** - Related to your own perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.
3. **Stapel Scale Rating** - Contains associators that you will rate according to your personal understanding and perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.
4. **Visual Perception Rating, and Assessment of Landscape Preference / Improvement** - Which seeks to assess how much the selected images matches your experiences and perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip at present and assesses which landscape elements may be included in the improvement of open spaces and streetscapes of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.

Ang survey questionnaire na ito ay binubuo ng apat na bahagi na kinabibilangan ng mga sumusunod na seksyon:

1. **Demograpikong Pagsisiyasat**- Kasama ang mga pangunahing tanong upang itala ang iyong demograpikong profile.
2. **Open-ended questions** - Kaugnay ng iyong sariling pananaw sa Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.
3. **Stapel Scale Rating** - Naglalaman ng mga associator na iyong ire-rate ayon sa iyong personal na pag-unawa at opinyon ukol sa Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.
4. **Visual Perception Rating, at Assessment of Landscape Preference / Improvement** - Naglalayong siyasatin kung gaano katugma ang mga napiling larawan sa iyong mga karanasan at pag-unawa sa Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip sa kasalukuyan at tinatasa kung aling mga *landscape element* ang maaaring isama sa pagpapabuti at pagsasa-ayos ng mga luntiang pook at mga lansangan ng Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.

To determine your eligibility to answer this survey, kindly check if you are: *

Upang malaman kung maari mong sagutan ang sarbey na ito, i-tsek kung ikaw ay:

- At least 15 years old (Hindi bababa sa 15-taong gulang)
- Familiar or has visited the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip more than once. (Pamilyar o nabisita na ang Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip higit sa isang beses)
- A Filipino citizen (Mamamayang Pilipino)

Bumalik

Susunod

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I-clear ang form

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DEMOGRAPHIC ASSESSMENT

This section aims to record your demographic profile.
Ang bahaging ito ay naglalayong itala ang iyong demographic profile.

Name (optional)
Pangalan (di-kinakailangan)

Iyong sagot _____

Sex assigned at birth *
Kasarian

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to disclose

Age *
Edad

- 15 - 17
- 18 - 24
- 25 - 34
- 35 - 44
- 45 - 54
- 55 - 64
- Above 65 (Higit sa 65)

Occupation *
Trabaho

- Employed for wages
- Self-employed
- Out of work and looking for work
- Homemaker
- Student
- Retired
- Unable to work
- Non-government Organization
- Design Professional
- Intermediary or community leader in Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip
- Business Owner in Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip

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Place of Residence *
Tirahan

Sta. Cruz, Manila

Quiapo, Manila

Outside Sta. Cruz or Quiapo, but within the city of Manila (Sa labas ng Sta. Cruz o Quiapo, ngunit sa loob ng lungsod ng Maynila)

Iba pa: _____

Length of Residency in Sta. Cruz or Quiapo, Manila *
Tagal ng paninirahan sa Sta. Cruz o sa Quiapo, Manila

Less than 5 years (Wala pang 5 taon)

5 to 10 years (Lima hanggang sampung taon)

More than 10 years (Higit pa sa sampung taon)

Not Applicable (Hindi naangkop)

Bumalik **Susunod** Page 3 ng 13 **I-clear ang form**

OPEN-ENDED QUESTIONS

In this section, you will be answering questions using your own words to avoid influencing your personal preferences and opinions.

Sa bahaging ito ay sasagutin mo ang mga sumunod na tanong gamit ang sarili mong mga pagkaunawa upang maiwasang maimpluwensyahan ang iyong mga personal na kagustuhan at opinyon.

What first comes into your mind when you hear or see the word "AVENIDA" or "RIZAL AVENUE"? *

Ano ang unang pumapasok sa isip mo kapag naririnig o nakikita mo ang salitang "AVENIDA" o "RIZAL AVENUE"?

lyong sagot _____

What do you think characterizes AVENIDA or RIZAL AVENUE? Are there any specific elements that stand out or characterizes AVENIDA or RIZAL AVENUE (from planting and materials to structures and architecture)? *

Ano sa tingin mo ang katangian ng AVENIDA o ng RIZAL AVENUE? Mayroon bang mga partikular na mga elemento ng hubog-lupa./landscape na namumukod-tangi o nagpapakita ng paghahakikilanlan ng AVENIDA o RIZAL AVENUE?

lyong sagot _____

What first comes into your mind when you hear or see the word "RECTO AVENUE"? *

Ano ang unang pumapasok sa isip mo kapag naririnig o nakikita mo ang salitang "RECTO AVENUE"?

lyong sagot _____

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What do you think characterizes RECTO AVENUE? Are there any specific elements that stand out or characterizes RECTO AVENUE (from planting and materials to structures and architecture)? *

Ano sa tingin mo ang katangian ng RECTO AVENUE? Mayroon bang mga partikular na mga elemento ng hubog-lupa/landscape na namumukod-tangi o nagpapakita ng pagkakahilanan ng RECTO AVENUE?

lyong sagot

What first comes into your mind when you hear or see the word "CARRIEDO STREET"? *

Ano ang unang pumapasok sa isip mo kapag naririnig o nakikita mo ang salitang "CARRIEDO STREET"?

lyong sagot

What do you think characterizes CARRIEDO STREET? Are there any specific elements that stand out or characterizes CARRIEDO STREET (from planting and materials to structures and architecture)? *

Ano sa tingin mo ang katangian ng CARRIEDO STREET? Mayroon bang mga partikular na mga elemento ng hubog-lupa/landscape na namumukod-tangi o nagpapakita ng pagkakahilanan ng CARRIEDO STREET?

lyong sagot

What three words would you choose to describe the term HERITAGE? *

Magbigay ng tatlong mga salitang kumakatawan sa terminong "HERITAGE" o "PAMANA".

lyong sagot

Bumalik Susunod Page 4 ng 13 I-clear ang form

STAPEL SCALE RATING

This section contains 35 "associators" or descriptors that you will rate according to your personal understanding and perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.

Ang bahaging ito ay naglalaman ng 35 na mga terminong ire-rate mo ayon sa iyong personal na pag-unawa at pananaw sa Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.

The rating ranges from -3 to 0 to +3, whereas:

- 3 = "I DO NOT think this is linked to my perception of what the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip is" (Sa tingin ko ay HINDI ito nauugnay sa aking pananaw kung ano ang Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip)
- 0 = "I think this is NEUTRAL to my perception of what the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip is" (Sa tingin ko ay NEUTRAL ito nauugnay sa aking pananaw kung ano ang Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip)
- +3 = "I REALLY THINK this is linked to my perception of what the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip is" (Sa tingin ko ay LABIS na NAUUGNAY ito sa aking pananaw kung ano ang Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.)

How close do you associate the following terms to your 'current' perception/opinion of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip? Rate from -3 (far from your perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip) to 0 (neutral) to +3 (close to your perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip). *

Gaano kalapit ang mga terminong ito sa iyong kasalukuyang pananaw o opinyon kung ano ang Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip? I-rate ang bawat isa mula -3 (malayo sa iyong pananaw ng Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip) hanggang +3 (malapit sa iyong pananaw ng Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.)

	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3
Shopping/Commercial District (Pamilihan, sentro ng komersyo)	<input type="radio"/>						
Major thoroughfare and Mass Transit (Pangunahing daanan)	<input type="radio"/>						
Busy pedestrian and motorist activities (Nagsisiksikang mga kompyuter at motorista)	<input type="radio"/>						

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Filthy, dark, narrow alleyways (Mga madilim, madumi, at masisikip na mga eskinita)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Congested, overcrowded, populous (Siksikan/Maraming tao)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Sociohistorical: Sites of important people and events (Mga lugar kung saan naganap ang mahahalagang pangyayari at mga tao)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Downtown Area / Red light district	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Informal Economy (Street vendors, hawking); Impormal na Ekonomiya (Mga nagtitinda sa kalye, hawking)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Petty Crimes, Violence and Illegal Activities (Pickpocketing, Gambling, Drug trafficking and Prostitution); Mga Malit na Krimen, Karahasan at Illegal na Aktibidad (Panunukot, Pagsusugal, Pagtutulak ng droga at Prostitusyon)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Light Rail Transit (LRT Lines 1 and 2)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Noisy, shabby, unclean, and polluted (Maingay, magulo, at marumi)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Movie houses / theatres, cultural arts, and vaudevilles (Mga sinehan, sining pangkultura, at teatro/tanghalan)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Urban decay, ill-planned, Disorderly, Deteriorated, Urban Blight (Hindi maayos na pag-paplano ng mga lugar, magulo, pagkabulok ng lugar)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Poor traffic conditions (Hindi magandang kondisyon ng trapiko)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Affordable goods and emporiums, retail, wholesale items (Abot-kayang mga produkto at emporium, tingian, pakyawan na mga paninda)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Battle of Manila, World War II (Labanan sa Maynila, Ikalawang Digmaang Pandaigdig)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Renamed Streets ex. Calle Iris, Calle Azcarraga, Calle Dulumbayan, Calle Salcedo (Mga pinalitang pangalan ng mga kalye)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Japanese Bazaar, Japanese settlements	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Church and Religious Sites and Orders, Christian and Muslim Communities (Mga Simbahan, Mga Pamayanang Kristiyano at Muslim)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Fiesta, Popular Devotions and Traditions (Mga pagdiriwang, popular na debosyon, at tradisyon)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
University Belt	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Tranvia and Horse-drawn Carriages (Tranvia at mga Kalesa)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Poverty, Slums, Informal Settlements, Beggars, Street Children (Kahirapan, Barong-barong, Mga pulubi, Mga Batang Lansangan)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Fake Documents/Counterfeit Items (Mga pekeng dokumento at paninda)	<input type="checkbox"/>						

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Economic center after Escolta (Sentro ng komersyo pagkatapos ng Escolta)	<input type="radio"/>						
Sociopolitical Organizations and Movements, Rallies and Demonstrations (Mga organisasyong at kilusang sosyopulitikal)	<input type="radio"/>						
Electronic goods, printing press, furniture shops, shoe marts, restaurants (Mga elektronikong kalakal, palimbagan, mga tindahan ng muwebles, mga tindahan ng sapatos, mga kainan)	<input type="radio"/>						
Marcos Era-projects, Martial law, First Quarter Storm (Proyekto noong panahon ni Marcos, Sr., Batas Militar, Sigwa ng Unang Sangkapat)	<input type="radio"/>						
Pasig River and Estuary (Ilog Pasig at mga Estero)	<input type="radio"/>						
Little Tokyo / Ginza of Manila	<input type="radio"/>						

Jeepneys	<input type="radio"/>						
Environmental and physical degradation (Pagkasira ng kapaligiran at pisikal na katangian ng lugar)	<input type="radio"/>						
Plazas (Plaza Miranda, Plaza Carriedo, Plaza Sta. Cruz)	<input type="radio"/>						
Buildings and Facilities Designed by Prominent Architects (Mga gusali at pasilidad na dinisensyo ng mga tanyag na arkitekto)	<input type="radio"/>						
Protection of illegal vending (Lagay, proteksyon ng ilegal na pagbebenta/paghahanap-buhay)	<input type="radio"/>						

Are there any additional things you would like to add regarding the image and/or identity of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip? *

Mayroon ka bang karagdagang opinyon tungkol sa imahe o/at sa paghahakilantan ng Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip?

Memoriscapes in Recto-spection: Visualizing Avenida, Recto, and Carriedo, Manila as Virtual Memoriscapes through immersive mobile technologies and digital heritage interpretation

VISUAL PERCEPTION RATING AND ASSESSMENT OF LANDSCAPE PREFERENCE / IMPROVEMENT

This section is linked to visual perception using Google Images and a 1 to 5 rating scale to assess how much the images match your experience of the present Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip. It also seeks to assess which landscape elements may be included in the improvement of open spaces and streetscapes of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.

Ang bahaging ito ay naglalayong imbestigahan ang biswal na pagunawa sa pamamagitan ng mga litrato mula sa Google Images, at isang rating scale mula 1 hanggang 5 upang malaman kung gaano tumutugma ang mga sumusunod na larawan sa inyong karanasan ng Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip sa hasalukuyan. Ito rin ay naglalayong malaman aling mga elemento sa landscape/pook ang maaring idagdag sa pagsasaayos ng mga open spaces at mga halsada ng Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.

Check the scale according to what best matches your experience/perception of the situation or scenery shown in the images. Rate from 1 (this does NOT match my experience of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip) to 5 (this HIGHLY MATCHES my experience of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.)

Suriin ang mga sumusunod na mga larawan ayon sa kung ano ang pinakatutugma sa inyong karanasan sa silwasyon o tanawin na ipinapakita sa mga larawan. I-rate ito mula 1 (HINDI ito tumutugma sa ating karanasan sa Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip) hanggang 5 (LABIS na TUMUTUGMA sa ating karanasan sa

Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip.)

IMAGE 1 (Photo credits: Alamy, Raya Capulong, ABS-CBN News)

To what extent does the set of images above capture or match your experience/perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip at present? *

Gaano katugma ang mga larawan sa itaas sa inyong karanasan sa hasalukuyang Recto Avenida Carriedo Strip?

1 2 3 4 5

DOES NOT MATCH (Hindi Tumutugma) HIGHLY MATCHES (Lubos na tumutugma)

If you think that the set of images HIGHLY MATCHES your experience/perception of the Recto-Avenida Carriedo Strip, please describe shortly what specific element/s of the image made it SIMILAR to your experience/perception. Write N/A if not applicable. *

Kung sa tingin mo ay TUMUTUGMA ang mga larawan sa inyong karanasan sa Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, mangyaring ilarawan kung anong mga partikular na mga elemento o aspeto na makikita sa larawan ang tumutugma sa inyong karanasan. Isulat ang N/A kung hindi ito naangkop.

Iyong sagot _____

If you think that the set of images DOES NOT MATCH your experience/perception of the Recto-Avenida Carriedo Strip, please describe shortly what specific element/s of the image made it NOT SIMILAR to your experience/perception. Write N/A if not applicable. *

Kung sa tingin mo ay HINDI TUMUTUGMA ang mga larawan sa inyong karanasan sa Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, mangyaring ilarawan kung anong mga partikular na mga elemento o aspeto na makikita sa larawan ang HINDI TUMUTUGMA sa inyong karanasan. Isulat ang N/A kung hindi ito naangkop.

Iyong sagot _____

Which facilities, equipment, or landscape element(s) should be added to this space for its improvement? Check all that apply. *

Aling mga pasilidad, kagamitan, o mga elemento sa landscape/pook ang maaring idagdag sa lugar na ito para sa pagsasaayos nito? Paki-tsek ang lahat ng naangkop.

- Children's Playground
- Al Fresco/Picnic Tables
- Benches
- Drinking fountain
- Public Restrooms
- Public Art Installations
- Information Board or Kiosk
- Interpretative Signages and Markers
- Wayfinding Signages
- Designated food stalls and eateries

Which facilities, equipment, or landscape element(s) should be added to this space for its improvement? Check all that apply. *

Aling mga pasilidad, kagamitan, o mga elemento sa landscape/pook ang maaring idagdag sa lugar na ito para sa pagsasaayos nito? Paki-tsek ang lahat ng naangkop.

- Children's Playground
- Al Fresco/Picnic Tables
- Benches
- Drinking fountain
- Public Restrooms
- Public Art Installations
- Information Board or Kiosk
- Interpretative Signages and Markers
- Wayfinding Signages
- Designated food stalls and eateries
- Designated Spaces for Stores and Kiosks
- Water Feature
- Bike Lane
- PUV Lanes
- Transport Bays
- Pedestrian Lane
- Public Parking Spaces
- Trash Receptacles
- Lamp Posts/Lighting Units
- Greenery/Planting
- Bollard
- PWD Ramps
- Pedestrian Crossing
- Police Outpost
- CCTV Units
- Gazebos and Pavillions
- Trees/Shrubbery
- Iba pa: _____

Bumalik Susunod Page 6 ng 13 I-clear ang form

Huwag isumite kailanman ang mga password sa pamamagitan ng Google Forms.

Ginawa ang form na ito sa University of the Philippines. Lulat ang [Pag-abuso](#)

VISUAL PERCEPTION RATING AND ASSESSMENT OF LANDSCAPE PREFERENCE / IMPROVEMENT

Image 2 out of 7

IMAGE 2 (Photo credits: Sidney Snoech, Guerrero Lester)

To what extent does the set of images above capture or match your experience/perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip at present?
Gaano kabugma ang mga larawan sa itaas sa iyong karanasan sa kasalukuyang Recto Avenida Carriedo Strip?

1 2 3 4 5

DOES NOT MATCH (Hindi Tumutugma) HIGHLY MATCHES (Lubos na tumutugma)

If you think that the set of images HIGHLY MATCHES your experience/perception of the Recto-Avenida Carriedo Strip, please describe shortly what specific element/s of the image made it SIMILAR to your experience/perception. Write N/A if not applicable.

Kung sa tingin mo ay TUMUTUGMA ang mga larawan sa iyong karanasan sa Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, mangyaring ilarawan lung anong mga partikular na mga elemento o aspeto na makilita sa larawan ang tumutugma sa iyong karanasan. Isulat ang N/A lung hindi ito naangkop.

Iyong sagot: _____

If you think that the set of images DOES NOT MATCH your experience/perception of the Recto-Avenida Carriedo Strip, please describe shortly what specific element/s of the image made it NOT SIMILAR to your experience/perception. Write N/A if not applicable.

Kung sa tingin mo ay HINDI TUMUTUGMA ang mga larawan sa iyong karanasan sa Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, mangyaring ilarawan lung anong mga partikular na mga elemento o aspeto na makilita sa larawan ang HINDI TUMUTUGMA sa iyong karanasan. Isulat ang N/A lung hindi ito naangkop.

Iyong sagot: _____

Which facilities, equipment, or landscape element(s) should be added to this space for its improvement? Check all that apply.
Aling mga pasilidad, kagamitan, o mga elemento sa landscape/pook ang maaring idigdag sa lugar na ito para sa pagsaayos nito? Paki-tsek ang lahat ng naangkop.

<input type="checkbox"/> Children's Playground (Palaruan)	<input type="checkbox"/> AI Fresco / Picnic Tables (Kainan)
<input type="checkbox"/> Benches (Upuan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Drinking fountain
<input type="checkbox"/> Public Restrooms (Palikuran)	<input type="checkbox"/> Public Art Installations (Mga sining/mural)
<input type="checkbox"/> Information Board or Kiosk	<input type="checkbox"/> Interpretative Signages and Markers
<input type="checkbox"/> Wayfinding Signages	<input type="checkbox"/> Designated food stalls and eateries (Kainan)
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

<input type="checkbox"/> Designated Spaces for Stores and Kiosks (Tindahan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Water Feature/Fountain
<input type="checkbox"/> Bike Lane	<input type="checkbox"/> PUV Lanes
<input type="checkbox"/> Transport Bays (Sakayan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Pedestrian Lane / Sidewalk
<input type="checkbox"/> Public Parking Spaces (Paradahang)	<input type="checkbox"/> Trash Receptacles (Basurahan)
<input type="checkbox"/> Lamp Posts/Lighting Units (Ilaw)	<input type="checkbox"/> Bollard
<input type="checkbox"/> PWD Ramps	<input type="checkbox"/> Pedestrian Crossing (Tawiran)
<input type="checkbox"/> Police Outpost	<input type="checkbox"/> CCTV Units
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

<input type="checkbox"/> Transport Bays (Sakayan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Pedestrian Lane / Sidewalk
<input type="checkbox"/> Public Parking Spaces (Paradahang)	<input type="checkbox"/> Trash Receptacles (Basurahan)
<input type="checkbox"/> Lamp Posts/Lighting Units (Ilaw)	<input type="checkbox"/> Bollard
<input type="checkbox"/> PWD Ramps	<input type="checkbox"/> Pedestrian Crossing (Tawiran)
<input type="checkbox"/> Police Outpost	<input type="checkbox"/> CCTV Units
<input type="checkbox"/> Gazebos and Pavilions	<input type="checkbox"/> Trees/Shrubbery/Greenery/Planting (Mga puno at halaman)
<input type="checkbox"/> Iba pa:	

Bumalik Susunod Page 7 ng 13 I-clear ang form

Howag isarile kailaman ang mga password sa pamamagitan ng Google Forms.

VISUAL PERCEPTION RATING AND ASSESSMENT OF LANDSCAPE PREFERENCE / IMPROVEMENT

Image 3 out of 7

IMAGE 3 (Photo credits: Sidney Snoeck, Walk With AL Youtube Channel)

To what extent does the set of images above capture or match your experience/perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip at present?
Gaano katugma ang mga larawan sa itaas sa iyong harapan sa kasalukuyang Recto Avenida Carriedo Strip?

1 2 3 4 5
DOES NOT MATCH (Hindi Tumutugma) ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ HIGHLY MATCHES (Lubos na tumutugma)

If you think that the set of images HIGHLY MATCHES your experience/perception of the Recto-Avenida Carriedo Strip, please describe shortly what specific element/s of the image made it SIMILAR to your experience/perception. Write N/A if not applicable.
Kung sa tingin mo ay TUMUTUGMA ang mga larawan sa iyong harapan sa Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, mangyaring ilarawan tung anong mga partikular na mga elemento o aspeto na makilala sa larawan ang tumutugma sa iyong harapan. Isulat ang N/A kung hindi ito naangkop.

Iyong sagot: _____

If you think that the set of images DOES NOT MATCH your experience/perception of the Recto-Avenida Carriedo Strip, please describe shortly what specific element/s of the image made it NOT SIMILAR to your experience/perception. Write N/A if not applicable.
Kung sa tingin mo ay HINDI TUMUTUGMA ang mga larawan sa iyong harapan sa Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, mangyaring ilarawan tung anong mga partikular na mga elemento o aspeto na makilala sa larawan ang tumutugma sa iyong harapan. Isulat ang N/A kung hindi ito naangkop.

Iyong sagot: _____

Which facilities, equipment, or landscape element(s) should be added to this space for its improvement? Check all that apply.
Aling mga pasilidad, kagamitan, o mga elemento sa landscape/pook ang maaring idagdag sa lugar na ito para sa pagsasayos nito? Paki-tsek ang lahat ng naangkop.

<input type="checkbox"/> Children's Playground (Palaruan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Al Fresco / Picnic Tables (Kainan)
<input type="checkbox"/> Benches (Upuan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Drinking fountain
<input type="checkbox"/> Public Restrooms (Palikuran)	<input type="checkbox"/> Public Art Installations (Mga sining/mural)
<input type="checkbox"/> Information Board or Kiosk	<input type="checkbox"/> Interpretative Signages and Markers
<input type="checkbox"/> Wayfinding Signages	<input type="checkbox"/> Designated food stalls and eateries (Kainan)

<input type="checkbox"/> Designated Spaces for Stores and Kiosks (Tindahan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Water Feature/Fountain
<input type="checkbox"/> Bike Lane	<input type="checkbox"/> PUV Lanes
<input type="checkbox"/> Transport Bays (Sakayan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Pedestrian Lane / Sidewalk
<input type="checkbox"/> Public Parking Spaces (Paradahan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Trash Receptacles (Basurahan)
<input type="checkbox"/> Lamp Posts/Lighting Units (Ilaw)	<input type="checkbox"/> Bollard
<input type="checkbox"/> PWD Ramps	<input type="checkbox"/> Pedestrian Crossing (Tawiran)
<input type="checkbox"/> Police Outpost	<input type="checkbox"/> CCTV Units

<input type="checkbox"/> Transport Bays (Sakayan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Pedestrian Lane / Sidewalk
<input type="checkbox"/> Public Parking Spaces (Paradahan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Trash Receptacles (Basurahan)
<input type="checkbox"/> Lamp Posts/Lighting Units (Ilaw)	<input type="checkbox"/> Bollard
<input type="checkbox"/> PWD Ramps	<input type="checkbox"/> Pedestrian Crossing (Tawiran)
<input type="checkbox"/> Police Outpost	<input type="checkbox"/> CCTV Units
<input type="checkbox"/> Gazebos and Pavilions	<input type="checkbox"/> Trees/Shrubbery/Greenery/Planting (Mga puno at halaman)
<input type="checkbox"/> Iba pa:	

Bumalik Susunod Page 8 ng 13 | I-clear ang form

VISUAL PERCEPTION RATING AND ASSESSMENT OF LANDSCAPE PREFERENCE / IMPROVEMENT

Image 5 out of 7

IMAGE 5 (Photo credits: Riel Diala)

To what extent does the set of images above capture or match your experience/perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip at present?
Ganoan hatugma ang mga larawan sa ilalag sa inyong karanasan sa kasalukuyang Recto Avenida Carriedo Strip?

1 2 3 4 5
DOES NOT MATCH (Hindi Tumutugma) ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ HIGHLY MATCHES (Lubos na tumutugma)

If you think that the set of images HIGHLY MATCHES your experience/perception of the Recto-Avenida Carriedo Strip, please describe shortly what specific element/s of the image made it SIMILAR to your experience/perception. Write N/A if not applicable.
Kung sa tingin mo ay TUMUTUGMA ang mga larawan sa inyong karanasan sa Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, mangyaring ilarawan kung anong mga partikular na mga elemento o aspeto na nakikita sa larawan ang tumutugma sa inyong karanasan. Isulat ang N/A kung hindi ito nangangkop.

Iyong sagot

If you think that the set of images DOES NOT MATCH your experience/perception of the Recto-Avenida Carriedo Strip, please describe shortly what specific element/s of the image made it NOT SIMILAR to your experience/perception. Write N/A if not applicable.
Kung sa tingin mo ay HINDI TUMUTUGMA ang mga larawan sa inyong karanasan sa Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, mangyaring ilarawan kung anong mga partikular na mga elemento o aspeto na nakikita sa larawan ang HINDI TUMUTUGMA sa inyong karanasan. Isulat ang N/A kung hindi ito nangangkop.

Iyong sagot

Which facilities, equipment, or landscape element(s) should be added to this space for its improvement? Check all that apply.
Aling mga pasilidad, kagamitan, o mga elemento sa landscape/pook ang mangaring idagdag sa lugar na ito para sa pagsasaayos nito? Paki-tsek ang lahat ng nangangkop.

<input type="checkbox"/> Children's Playground (Palaruan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Al Fresco / Picnic Tables (Kainan)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Benches (Upuan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Drinking fountain
<input type="checkbox"/> Public Restrooms (Palikuran)	<input type="checkbox"/> Public Art Installations (Mga sining/mural)
<input type="checkbox"/> Information Board or Kiosk	<input type="checkbox"/> Interpretative Signages and Markers
<input type="checkbox"/> Wayfinding Signages	<input type="checkbox"/> Designated food stalls and eateries (Kainan)

<input type="checkbox"/> Designated Spaces for Stores and Kiosks (Tindahan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Water Feature/Fountain
<input type="checkbox"/> Bike Lane	<input type="checkbox"/> PUV Lanes
<input type="checkbox"/> Transport Bays (Sakayan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Pedestrian Lane / Sidewalk
<input type="checkbox"/> Public Parking Spaces (Paradahan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Trash Receptacles (Basurahan)
<input type="checkbox"/> Lamp Posts/Lighting Units (Ilaw)	<input type="checkbox"/> Bollard
<input type="checkbox"/> PWD Ramps	<input type="checkbox"/> Pedestrian Crossing (Tawiran)
<input type="checkbox"/> Police Outpost	<input type="checkbox"/> CCTV Units

<input type="checkbox"/> Transport Bays (Sakayan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Pedestrian Lane / Sidewalk
<input type="checkbox"/> Public Parking Spaces (Paradahan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Trash Receptacles (Basurahan)
<input type="checkbox"/> Lamp Posts/Lighting Units (Ilaw)	<input type="checkbox"/> Bollard
<input type="checkbox"/> PWD Ramps	<input type="checkbox"/> Pedestrian Crossing (Tawiran)
<input type="checkbox"/> Police Outpost	<input type="checkbox"/> CCTV Units
<input type="checkbox"/> Gazebos and Pavilions	<input type="checkbox"/> Trees/Shrubbery/Greenery/Planting (Mga puno at halaman)
<input type="checkbox"/> Iba pa:	

Bumalik Susunod Page 9 ng 13 I-clear ang form

Harap isumite kailanman ang mga password sa pamamagitan ng Google Forms.
Ginawa ang form na ito sa University of the Philippines. Isulat ang Pap-abuso

Google Forms

VISUAL PERCEPTION RATING AND ASSESSMENT OF LANDSCAPE PREFERENCE / IMPROVEMENT

Image 6 out of 7

IMAGE 6 (Photo credits: Julie Gilbero, Alamy)

To what extent does the set of images above capture or match your experience/perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip at present?
Gaano katugma ang mga larawan sa itaas sa iyong haranasan sa kasalutuyang Recto Avenida Carriedo Strip?

1 2 3 4 5
DOES NOT MATCH (Hindi Tumutugma) ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ HIGHLY MATCHES (Lubos na tumutugma)

If you think that the set of images HIGHLY MATCHES your experience/perception of the Recto-Avenida Carriedo Strip, please describe shortly what specific element/s of the image made it SIMILAR to your experience/perception. Write N/A if not applicable.
Kung sa tingin mo ay TUMUTUGMA ang mga larawan sa iyong haranasan sa Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, mangyaring ilarawan kung anong mga partikular na mga elemento o aspeto na mahikita sa larawan ang HINDI tumutugma sa iyong haranasan. Isulat ang N/A kung hindi ito naangkop.

Iyong sagot

If you think that the set of images DOES NOT MATCH your experience/perception of the Recto-Avenida Carriedo Strip, please describe shortly what specific element/s of the image made it NOT SIMILAR to your experience/perception. Write N/A if not applicable.
Kung sa tingin mo ay HINDI TUMUTUGMA ang mga larawan sa iyong haranasan sa Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, mangyaring ilarawan kung anong mga partikular na mga elemento o aspeto na mahikita sa larawan ang HINDI tumutugma sa iyong haranasan. Isulat ang N/A kung hindi ito naangkop.

Iyong sagot

Which facilities, equipment, or landscape elements should be added to this space for its improvement? Check all that apply.
Aling mga pasilidad, kagamitan, o mga elemento sa landscape/pook ang maaring idagdag sa lugar na ito para sa pagsasaayos nito? Paki-tsek ang lahat ng naangkop.

<input type="checkbox"/> Children's Playground (Palaruan)	<input type="checkbox"/> AI Fresco / Picnic Tables (Kainan)
<input type="checkbox"/> Benches (Upuan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Drinking fountain
<input type="checkbox"/> Public Restrooms (Palikuran)	<input type="checkbox"/> Public Art Installations (Mga string/mural)
<input type="checkbox"/> Information Board or Kiosk	<input type="checkbox"/> Interpretative Signages and Markers
<input type="checkbox"/> Wayfinding Signages	<input type="checkbox"/> Designated food stalls and eateries (Kainan)

<input type="checkbox"/> Designated Spaces for Stores and Kiosks (Tindahan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Water Feature/Fountain
<input type="checkbox"/> Bike Lane	<input type="checkbox"/> PUV Lanes
<input type="checkbox"/> Transport Bays (Sakayan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Pedestrian Lane / Sidewalk
<input type="checkbox"/> Public Parking Spaces (Paradahan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Trash Receptacles (Basurahan)
<input type="checkbox"/> Lamp Posts/Lighting Units (Ilaw)	<input type="checkbox"/> Bollard
<input type="checkbox"/> PWD Ramps	<input type="checkbox"/> Pedestrian Crossing (Tawiran)
<input type="checkbox"/> Police Outpost	<input type="checkbox"/> CCTV Units

<input type="checkbox"/> Transport Bays (Sakayan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Pedestrian Lane / Sidewalk
<input type="checkbox"/> Public Parking Spaces (Paradahan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Trash Receptacles (Basurahan)
<input type="checkbox"/> Lamp Posts/Lighting Units (Ilaw)	<input type="checkbox"/> Bollard
<input type="checkbox"/> PWD Ramps	<input type="checkbox"/> Pedestrian Crossing (Tawiran)
<input type="checkbox"/> Police Outpost	<input type="checkbox"/> CCTV Units
<input type="checkbox"/> Gazebo and Pavilions	<input type="checkbox"/> Trees/Shrubbery/Greenery/Planting (Mga puno at halaman)
<input type="checkbox"/> Iba pa:	

Bumalik Susunod Page 9 ng 13 I-clear ang form

Hawag isumite kailanman ang mga password sa pamamagitan ng Google Forms.
Ginawa ang form na ito sa University of the Philippines. Lulat ang Dagabao

Google Forms

VISUAL PERCEPTION RATING AND ASSESSMENT OF LANDSCAPE PREFERENCE / IMPROVEMENT

Image 7 out of 7

IMAGE 7 (Photo credits: Riel Dida, Google Earth Street Imagery)

To what extent does the set of images above capture or match your experience/perception of the Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip at present?
Gaano katugma ang mga larawan sa itaas sa iyong karanasan sa kasalukuyang Recto Avenida Carriedo Strip?

1 2 3 4 5
DOES NOT MATCH (Hindi Tumutugma) ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ HIGHLY MATCHES (Lubos na tumutugma)

If you think that the set of images HIGHLY MATCHES your experience/perception of the Recto-Avenida Carriedo Strip, please describe shortly what specific element/s of the image made it SIMILAR to your experience/perception. Write N/A if not applicable.
Kung sa tingin mo ay TUMUTUGMA ang mga larawan sa iyong karanasan sa Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, mangyaring ikarawan iung anong mga partikular na mga elemento o aspeto na makikita sa larawan ang tumutugma sa iyong karanasan. Isulat ang N/A kung hindi ito naangkop.

Iyong sagot _____

If you think that the set of images DOES NOT MATCH your experience/perception of the Recto-Avenida Carriedo Strip, please describe shortly what specific element/s of the image made it NOT SIMILAR to your experience/perception. Write N/A if not applicable.
Kung sa tingin mo ay HINDI TUMUTUGMA ang mga larawan sa iyong karanasan sa Recto-Avenida-Carriedo Strip, mangyaring ikarawan iung anong mga partikular na mga elemento o aspeto na makikita sa larawan ang HINDI TUMUTUGMA sa iyong karanasan. Isulat ang N/A kung hindi ito naangkop.

Iyong sagot _____

Which facilities, equipment, or landscape element(s) should be added to this space for its improvement? Check all that apply.
Aling mga pasilidad, kagamitan, o mga elemento sa landscape/pook ang maaring idagdag sa lugar na ito para sa pagsasagayon nito? Paki-tsek ang lahat ng naangkop.

<input type="checkbox"/> Children's Playground (Palaruan)	<input type="checkbox"/> AI Fresco / Picnic Tables (Kainan)
<input type="checkbox"/> Benches (Upuan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Drinking fountain
<input type="checkbox"/> Public Restrooms (Palikuran)	<input type="checkbox"/> Public Art Installations (Mga sining/mural)
<input type="checkbox"/> Information Board or Kiosk	<input type="checkbox"/> Interpretative Signages and Markers
<input type="checkbox"/> Wayfinding Signages	<input type="checkbox"/> Designated food stalls and eateries (Kainan)

<input type="checkbox"/> Designated Spaces for Stores and Kiosks (Tindahan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Water Feature/Fountain
<input type="checkbox"/> Bike Lane	<input type="checkbox"/> PUV Lanes
<input type="checkbox"/> Transport Bays (Sakayan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Pedestrian Lane / Sidewalk
<input type="checkbox"/> Public Parking Spaces (Paradahan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Trash Receptacles (Basurahan)
<input type="checkbox"/> Lamp Posts/Lighting Units (Ilaw)	<input type="checkbox"/> Bollard
<input type="checkbox"/> PWD Ramps	<input type="checkbox"/> Pedestrian Crossing (Tawiran)
<input type="checkbox"/> Police Outpost	<input type="checkbox"/> CCTV Units

<input type="checkbox"/> Transport Bays (Sakayan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Pedestrian Lane / Sidewalk
<input type="checkbox"/> Public Parking Spaces (Paradahan)	<input type="checkbox"/> Trash Receptacles (Basurahan)
<input type="checkbox"/> Lamp Posts/Lighting Units (Ilaw)	<input type="checkbox"/> Bollard
<input type="checkbox"/> PWD Ramps	<input type="checkbox"/> Pedestrian Crossing (Tawiran)
<input type="checkbox"/> Police Outpost	<input type="checkbox"/> CCTV Units
<input type="checkbox"/> Gazebos and Pavilions	<input type="checkbox"/> Trees/Shrubbery/Greenery/Planting (Mga puno at halaman)
<input type="checkbox"/> Iba pa: _____	

Bumalik Susunod Page 9 ng 13 I-clear ang form

Hawag isumite kailanman ang mga password sa pamamagitan ng Google Forms.
Ginawa ang form na ito sa University of the Philippines. Isulat ang Pag-abaso

Google Forms

Memoriscapes in Recto-spection: Visualizing Avenida, Recto, and Carriedo, Manila as Virtual Memoriscapes through immersive mobile technologies and digital heritage interpretation

END OF SURVEY

Thank you for taking your time in completing this survey. I sincerely appreciate your assistance valuable insights for the conduct of my study entitled **"Memoriscapes in Recto-spection: Envisioning Avenida, Recto, and Carriedo, Manila as Virtual Memoriscapes Through Immersive Mobile Technologies and Digital Heritage Interpretation"**.

If you are interested to know about the outcome of this survey, kindly include your email address in this form so that I may contact you about the survey results and findings.

Lastly, should you have any other concerns or comments, kindly reach out to me through this email address. lyalianza@up.edu.ph

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Maraming salamat para sa inyong oras sa pagtatapos ng sarbey na ito. Ang inyong mga sagot ay lubhang makakatulong sa paggawa ng aking tesis na pinamagatang, "Memoriscapes in Recto-spection: Envisioning Avenida, Recto, and Carriedo, Manila as Virtual Memoriscapes Through Immersive Mobile Technologies and Digital Heritage Interpretation".

Kung kayo ay interesado sa resulta ng pag-aaral na ito, mangyaring ilagay ang inyong email address sa ibaba upang kayo ay mabigyan ng kopya ng resulta ng sarbey na ito.

Kung kayo naman ay may mga karagdagang tanong o mga komento, mangyaring i-contact ako sa pamamagitan ng email sa lyalianza@up.edu.ph.

Email Address *

lyong sagot

Would you like to receive the results of this survey? *

By agreeing to this question, I will send you an email containing the survey results within 1-2 weeks.

Gusto niyo bang makakuha ng resulta ng sarbey na ito?

Sa pag-ayon sa tanong na ito ay makakakuha kayo ng email na naglalaman ng kahihinatnan ng sarbey na ito sa loob ng 1 - 2 na linggo

- Yes
 No

Would you like to take part in a co-design workshop session on May 13, 2023, *
from 8:30 AM to 4:00 PM?

By agreeing to this question, I will screen your eligibility to take part in the workshop session. Kindly expect an email from me containing the details of the workshop within 1 - 2 weeks. Selected participants would be incentivized with 500 PHP, certificate of participation, token of appreciation, food, and transportation allowance to the venue.

Nais niyo bang maging bahagi ng isang co-design workshop session sa Mayo 13, 2023 sa ganap na 8:30 AM hanggang 4:00 PM?

Sa pamamagitan ng pagsang-ayon sa tanong na ito, susuriin ko ang iyong pagiging karapat-dapat na makilahok sa sesyon ng workshop. Mangyaring asahan ang isang email mula sa akin na naglalaman ng mga detalye ng workshop sa loob ng 1 - 2 linggo. Ang mga piling kalahok ay mabibigyan ng insentibo ng 500 PHP, certificate of participation, token of appreciation, food, at transportation allowance sa venue.

- Yes
 No

If you answered YES to the previous question, kindly add your Facebook link and contact number for the participant database.

Kung OO ang sagot mo sa nakaraang tanong, mangyaring idagdag ang iyong Facebook link at contact number para sa database ng kalahok.

lyong sagot

Would you like to take part in the raffle as an incentive for answering this survey? *

Get a chance to be one of five respondents to win 200 PHP once the quota has been reached.

Gusto mo bang makilahok sa raffle bilang insentibo sa pagsagot sa survey na ito?

Magkaroon ng pagkakataong maging isa sa limang respondent na manalo ng 200 PHP kapag naabot na ang quota.

- Yes
 No

Nais niyo bang maging bahagi ng isang co-design workshop session sa Mayo 13, 2023 sa ganap na 8:30 AM hanggang 4:00 PM?

Sa pamamagitan ng pagsang-ayon sa tanong na ito, susuriin ko ang iyong pagiging karapat-dapat na makilahok sa sesyon ng workshop. Mangyaring asahan ang isang email mula sa akin na naglalaman ng mga detalye ng workshop sa loob ng 1 - 2 linggo. Ang mga piling kalahok ay mabibigyan ng insentibo ng 500 PHP, certificate of participation, token of appreciation, food, at transportation allowance sa venue.

- Yes
 No

If you answered YES to the previous question, kindly add your Facebook link and contact number for the participant database.

Kung OO ang sagot mo sa nakaraang tanong, mangyaring idagdag ang iyong Facebook link at contact number para sa database ng kalahok.

lyong sagot

Would you like to take part in the raffle as an incentive for answering this survey? *

Get a chance to be one of five respondents to win 200 PHP once the quota has been reached.

Gusto mo bang makilahok sa raffle bilang insentibo sa pagsagot sa survey na ito?

Magkaroon ng pagkakataong maging isa sa limang respondent na manalo ng 200 PHP kapag naabot na ang quota.

- Yes
 No

If you answered YES to the previous question, kindly add your Facebook link and GCash number to be included in the raffle.

Kung OO ang sagot mo sa nakaraang tanong, paki-add ang iyong Facebook link at GCash number para maisama sa raffle.

lyong sagot

Bumalik

Submit

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